

SOME FACTS ABOUT JAPANESE LIDERSHIP STYLE

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Annotation: This article describes a set of three important ideas that we can learn from Japan. They can have a broad impact on the quality of our executive decision-making, our corporate planning, employee productivity, and management skills.

Key words: Corporate culture, leadership, Japanese method, Whitehill, team competition, adequate, communication, individuality.

Businessmen in the United States and Europe recognize Japanese industry as an important supplier, customer, and competitor. But they also need to know this as teachers. The reason is that Japan has reached the pinnacle of its role model by creating its own model.

Let's look at the experience of Japan. What stands out in the history of Japan, as well as in the behavior of Japanese management today, is the ability to make 180-degree turns, that is, the ability to come to radical and highly controversial decisions. I will describe: No country was more receptive to Christianity than Japan in the 16th century. Indeed, the Portuguese missionaries' hope that Japan would become the first Christian country outside of Europe was not just a dream. Nevertheless, this same Japan made a 180-degree turn at the beginning of the 17th century. Within a few years he completely suppressed Christianity and shut himself off from all foreign influence, certainly from any contact with the outside world, and remained so for 250 years. Then, in the Meiji Restoration of 1867, Japan made another 180-degree turn and opened itself up to the West—something no other European country could do. Toyo Rayon, the largest producer of man-made fibers, produced only rayon in the mid-1950s. Then he decided to switch to synthetic fibers. But the district did not "phase out" production, as every Western company in a similar situation does.

Instead, it closed its district mills overnight, even though under Japan's employment system it could not lay off 1 employee. It can be considered that such decision-making and discussion of each decision in each branch is a manifestation of the Japanese model in management. Now, if we look specifically at the leadership potential of personnel management, US-American concepts of personnel management have universal validity. In fact, these concepts have been used throughout the world for decades without regard to local cultures. Japan is no exception. Most Japanese organizations also use models such as Management by Objectives. However, the Japanese have very different expectations and behaviors than people in the western world.

Some European leaders may wonder what adequate leadership and

communication with the Japanese people should look like. Japanese culture responds to this. It is the patience and self-sacrifice of the Japanese people, and the fact that they consider social development as development, that defines their unique behavior.

In addition, the Japanese demonstrated at this early period that they were adept at taking ideas from abroad and adapting them to their own circumstances. For example, they developed Mahayana Buddhism as a Japanese form of Buddhism.

Managers in both Western countries and Japan emphasize the importance of human resource management for organizations. However, there is a big difference between these two cultures: the Japanese apply this principle very deeply. Many examples can be found in the speech of Keizaburo Yamada, Vice President of the Board of Directors of Mitsubishi Corporation (MC):

MC is a company of 10,000 employees with a shared destiny. Management should seek to understand the views of ordinary employees and vice versa. Considering that employees are part of the main assets of a Japanese company, it is understandable that a lot of attention is paid to their well-being.

"Workers in Japanese companies are members of a group, and they belong to groups rather than to individual employees" (Coulmas, 2014, Article 3133). Whitehill expresses the same principle by quoting M.Y. Yoshino, professor and director of research at Harvard Business School: The basic unit in an organization is the team, not the individual. He says. This is one of the main differences between American and Japanese management.

There is a fundamental difference with the West in hiring employees. Japanese companies do not hire candidates for a specific position within the company, and employees are likely to join the company for life. Such an arrangement obviously implies a very different relationship between employer and employee compared to, for example, the United States, where workers are always treated as interchangeable resources.

Functions are vaguely described at the individual level because individual employees do not receive assignments because they are assigned to a team. Interactions at the team level are fluid, so collaboration between teams is encouraged instead of "guarding your turf". Japanese employees go through a number of trial stages to get a new job and may work for a short period of time for low pay, but these challenges are not for temporary work. Employees are diligent about their small tasks and if their working hours start at 09:00 even going to work at 08:30 is considered late. Japanese employees also spend a lot of time organizing collective bargaining in relation to work. This type of behavior, which we consider professional dedication, has become a permanent tradition for

all Japanese employees today.

In Japan's achievement of the peak of growth today, development starts from the internal environment, development starts from transparency, development begins from democracy and collectiveness, and the goal of today's enterprises is to use less resources, get more profit, create jobs, expand production, and realize this goal. he was able to demonstrate the importance of the need for effective organization of activities, and one of the factors influencing this activity is the growing popularity of corporate culture.

Corporate culture is a way to make transparent, fair, timely and decisive decisions of the enterprise. The Japanese management system is recognized as the most effective in the world, and the main reason for its success is the ability to work with people. We know that although Japan is a poor country in terms of natural resources, today it is occupying the world markets with its equipment and technologies.

Japan was the first in the world to develop modern management and developed the principle of our wealth, human resources. In recent years, almost all countries in the world are interested in Japanese management. Because the rapid and successful development of this country made it possible to take a leading position in the world. Japan is recognized as the most competitive country in the world: it occupies a leading position in ensuring the quality of literacy, social and political life.

So what is the secret of Japan's leadership today?

What is the impact of corporate culture on this?

If we look at the stage of development of Japan, it developed partly as a result of local customs and partly as a reaction to the conflict with America after the Second World War and the need to fight against destruction. According to many people, Japan is still a country of pineapples, and partly so. Because in almost all spheres of Japan's activity, its national traditions lead. In Japan, the future plans of any employee of the organization reflect the established goals, development schedule and development stages. This approach determines the transparency of information and appropriate relationships in the team in each corporation. Strengthens corporate relations. Managers in both Western countries and Japan emphasize the importance of human resource management for organizations. However, there is a big difference between the cultures of these two regions. The Japanese approach this principle very carefully.

The Japanese prefer team competition to individual competition. It is emphasized that the Japanese method of competition is teamwork. Also, one of the secrets of Japanese leadership is the effective use of unique forms of communication. The

Japanese prefer and support lifetime employment and employee tenure and coverage. The Japanese, like the Chinese, but unlike Western Europeans and Americans, are very strict about keeping quiet in their meetings. Silence is not used for relaxation, but rather for personal reflection. One of the unique aspects of Japanese corporate culture is that decision-making is collective and understandable and clear to all employees.

In order for Japan to become a leader in today's world, first of all, it carefully organized the corporate culture of Western Europe and the United States, adapted it to its own nationalism, and created its own corporate culture.

This culture has reached its peak with a number of advantages. Concepts somewhat outdated in Western Europe and the USA: loyalty, traditionalism, hard work, discipline, loyalty to authority, self-control, sense of duty, politeness form the basis of Japanese corporate culture.

The Japanese people always emphasize that they have only one wealth. Here, Akio Morito says in his book *Made in Japan: The secret of Japanese leadership* is not in any theory or secret recipe, program or government policy cannot make an enterprise successful, only people can do it.

The majority of Japan's population is Japanese. In this regard, almost all the employees of the company are Japanese. The most important task of Japanese leaders is to establish normal relations with employees, to create an understanding that the fate of workers and managers is one. Naturally, the company's culture and traditions are under the spirit of one nation, which makes management much easier.

Based on the above points, corporate culture is not a culture that is formed by copying or borrowing, it includes the core values of the company or firm.

It can also be seen that the transfer of organizational behavior from one soil to another usually fails.

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